

Optimization of Mudharabah Covenants in Sharia Banking

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Abstract: The principle of mudharabah is a unique part of Islamic banking products, because it has a philosophical difference between the conventional banking system and Islamic banking which adheres to the principle of profit or loss. Mudharabah is a partnership business covering capital owners (Shahib al-mal) and business actors (mudharib), aiming to gain profit (al-ribh) and divided according to agreement in the contract. This research is library research. While this research approach uses a statute approach, because the problems in this study are approached with positive legal norms and Islamic law. The purpose of writing scientific papers is to determine the extent to which Islamic banking in optimizing Mudharabah contracts as products in Islamic banking. The results of this study are one of the institutions that can guarantee the continued maintenance of compliance with Sharia or Islamic law is the DSN-MUI which gives sharia compliance compliance authorities (Shariah Compliance) is the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS). The implementation of the Mudharabah contract in the Islamic banking system is one form of banking compliance with the sharia principles that DPS-MUI has applied to Islamic banking.

Keywords: Mudharabah Agreement, Islamic Banking, DSN-MUI Fatwa

I. Introduction

Banking is an institution that has a very significant role in the development of a country. This role is manifested in the function of banks as financial intermediary institutions, namely those tasked with raising funds from the public in the form of savings and loans and forms of distribution with credit or other forms that can improve people's lives.

Indonesia as a country with the largest Muslim population was inhabited only at the end of the 20th century in which the cultural system which was rooted and entrenched was based on the shari'ah principle so that it became a significant value in building banks based on Islamic sharia . At the beginning of the establishment of sharia banks in Indonesia, they still held fast to the conventional banking system which became a benchmark for financial institutions at the time, but after the development of international sharia banking which began with the presence of foreign ministers held by the Islamic Conference Organization in Karachi, Pakistan, in the 70s. While in the 80s Islamic banks appeared in Egypt, Sudan, Pakistan, Iran, Malaysia, Bangladesh and Turkey. In 1983 a policy package was issued relating to the granting of interest rate flexibility so that finally in 1988 a policy was issued to build new banks.

Institutionally the Sharia Bank which was first established in Indonesia was PT Bank Muamalah Indonesia to run all operational Shari'ah-based financial institutions. However, the establishment of Bank Muamalah Indonesia was originally sparked in a MUI workshop which at the time had the theme of the problem of bank interest and banking at that time interest in conventional banking greatly explored the Indonesian banking world. After the formation of the Bank Muamalah Indonesia institution, other sharia-based banks emerged (Khotibul Umam, 2015).

One distinctive feature of sharia financial institutions is the existence of the Sharia Supervisory Board. The Sharia Supervisory Board has a very important influence in operating the operational system in sharia banking. Therefore the Shari'ah Supervisory Board has the responsibility to better ensure the application of the system in accordance with the sharia principles so that it can be implemented optimally.

In optimizing the National Sharia Council-Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) and the Sharia Supervisory Board have very heavy responsibilities in the supervision of sharia banking to conform to sharia principles in the economic sector. Good and bad in the operation of Islamic banks is very influential on the religion of Islam which is the main role

model of sharia principles, even if the banking system violates the principles set by the DSN-MUI fatwa, then the community will not only blame the Islamic bank but will blame the religion of Islam and will not even believe it. again and assume if Islam does not have a good economic system and violates the principles of justice and equity that are the grip in Islamic law itself. Therefore transactions in sharia banking must be adjusted to the principles of sharia that have been contained in fiqhiyah rules.

In conformity with sharia principles, DSN-MUI issues fatwas based on the Qur'an and Al-Hadith which are the main sources in decision making. It's just that the presence of Islamic financial institutions requires serious efforts to disseminate to the public about Islamic banking products that are in accordance with the concept of maqoshid al-sharia and equity of the community's economy (Muhammad Firdaus, 2005).

Maqasid syariah has the main goal of realizing the Islamic economic system, including Islamic banks. The implication of the goal of Maqasid Sharia is not just a goal to be able to meet all the needs of the community, but can realize growth and justice in 5 aspects of the sharia goals of religion, reason, ancestry, wealth and honor (Ahmes H., 2014).

In muamalah, the transaction law in muamalah is permissible unless there is an argument that prohibits the transaction. This rule can have implications for every muamalah activity in Islam is very broad, providing innovations that are appreciated and new transactions can be accepted in meeting the needs of banks in running the economy of society. Prohibition of transactions in bermuamalah can be simplified by three things namely: Riba, Gharar and Maysir which has become a prohibition in carrying out the system of Islamic principles. Broadly speaking, the product distribution of funds to the public in the Islamic banking system is in the form of financing based on a sale and purchase agreement that can be beneficial to both parties. Fundraising activities from the public are known as financing based on the desired real profit or profit sharing. One of the juridical characteristics in the Islamic finance industry is the regulation of Shariah compliance which is the basis and principle of its operations.

Sharia compliance is a very important part in terms of management and the operational system. Such a case is strongly supported by the existence of the Sharia Supervisory Board for every bank financial institution based on sharia or Islamic law. DPS is tasked with supervising the application of the operating system in the banking sector starting from the contract or contract applied to the Islamic banking. In connection with this description, a fatwa was issued by the National Sharia Council and Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) and the importance of the existence of DPS as an important aspect in overseeing the compliance of sharia for sharia financial industry regulations.

II. Literature Review

Mudharabah comes from the word dharb which means to hit or wander / travel to trade in developing a business he has, to be more precise it can be said of someone who is hitting or putting his foot on a business trip. Mudharabah is also called Qiradh which is taken by the word Al-Qardh which means to cut (Ahmad Dahlan, 2012), because humans in general and specifically from the owners and recipients of capital are inseparable from the goal in order to achieve profits and can develop their business and can be taken by continew (Enang Hidayat, 2016).

According to the term Mudharabah fiqh is a contract between two parties where one party gives up money / capital to the other party for trading where the profit is divided in two according to the agreement agreed by both parties (Syarif Hidayatullah, 2012). According to Adiwarman A. Karim, Mudharabah is a form of cooperation contract between two parties where one party acts as the owner of the capital and the other party breperan as the manager of the capital for a business that can generate profits and then will be divided into two results obtained in accordance with the agreement which was agreed at the beginning (Syarif Hidayatullah, 2012).

Financing with a Mudharabah agreement is one of the financing that is fully deferred for the capital of a business issued by the bank to the recipient of capital as the operator of the business. Through this financing the bank or capital recipient is entitled to receive the results of the business carried out by the recipient of capital continuously as long as the business is still running. While the profits are shared based on the agreement of both parties that have been signed at the beginning of the contract.

If the management of a bankrupt business is in progress, the party will bear it as long as the mistake is not intentional by the recipient of the capital, but if the bankruptcy is caused by the negligence factor of the recipient of the capital, the recipient of the capital has the right to be responsible for the losses he has done. Therefore the Bank has an interest so

that public funds collected can be channeled back to the public conducive and safe, so that with a more conducive distribution, banks will benefit from a profit sharing system both for banks and for depositing funds (Wangsawidjaja, 2012).

In the application of mudharabah contract, it can be known by several types in Mudharabah contract products, namely: First, Mudharabah Mutlaqoh, is cooperation between the first party and the second party which has a wider scope, the meaning is not limited by time, business specifications and business area. Second, Mudharabah Muqayyadah, is the opposite of the Mutlaqah Mudharabah contract which is limited by time, business specifications, and areas of business (Khaerul Umam, 2013).

In today's modern banking practice both forms of Mudharabah have changed in terms of the Mudharabah muqayyadah on balance sheet and Mudharabah Muqayyadah off balance sheet. According to pertaman flow namely Mudharabah on balance sheet is a one-fund flow for a group of business operators in a number of limited sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing and services, and this scheme is recorded in the bank's balance sheet. Meanwhile, according to the second flow of funds is devoted to financing only one bank account and the bank only acts as an arranger, while the profit sharing system depends on the agreement of investors and customers as managers of funds / capital (Adiwarman Karim, 2006).

Journal of Law Luqman Nurhisam, "Sharia Compliance in the Islamic Finance Industry". The journal explained that the existence of the Sharia Supervisory Board in each Sharia Bank Financial Industry and Sharia Non-Bank Financial Industry It was obliged to comply with sharia provisions making sharia supervision an inseparable part of sharia compliance. This can be seen from several regulations issued by DPS-MUI which serve as a reference for the IKBS and IKNBS industries in carrying out their activities in the field of Islamic finance. This research focuses on regulations issued by DSN-MUI and their implementation of the IKBS and IKNBS institutions, and DPS as the authorized party to oversee every sharia-based financial industry.

The Islamic finance and accounting journal, Sepky Mardian, "Sharia compliance levels in Islamic Financial Institutions", in the article explained that Shariah compliance is among the aspects that distinguish Islamic economics from conventional economics or between Islamic banking and conventional banking. In the banking context, this is a crucial issue, because until now, Islamic banks are suspected to still be following conventional banks in terms of products, human resources or operations. In this study it can be concluded that as the development of the Islamic economy,

especially Islamic financial institutions require the fulfillment of Islamic principles. DSN-MUI and DPS as parties who provide guarantees for sharia compliance have attempted. Until now there have been 95 fatwas issued. However, various limitations, especially resources, cause the enforcement of sharia compliance has not been running optimally. Besides that, there are many rational people who are not ready to use the principles of sharia purely to contribute to the non-fulfillment of sharia principles. In the future, all parties including the community must continue to support the development of the Islamic economy with a high level of sharia compliance.

III. Methodology

This research is a library research that is the research conducted based only on written works, including the results of research both those that have been and have not been published (Arikunto, 2000). While this research approach uses the statute approach, because the problems in this study are approached with positive legal norms and Islamic law.

IV. Results

Positive law is a law in which the legislation is legal which is constitutionally valid in a country, where the system of formation is in accordance with the procedure for the formation of legislation in the Unitary State. The policies contained in the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia can affect the banking system as its main principle. Sharia banking policy in Indonesia was formulated since 1992 based on Law Number 7 of 1992 concerning banking although the regulation has not yet comprehensively governed the Islamic economic system, however, the amendment reflects the points on sharia banking in the future.

In this case formally before 1992 the sharia banking system was not yet legal about legal issues that had a character without interest and were based on sharia principles or Islamic law. In 2008 the Indonesian government enacted Law Number 21 of 2008 concerning Islamic banking which was ratified on June 17, 2008, whose enactment was listed in the

State Gazette on July 16, 2008. The intended law introduced several new legal institutions that were appointed to support the implementation of development in order to improve justice, togetherness and even distribution of people's welfare (Khotibul Umam, 2011).

Mudharabah contract regulation in Act Number 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking is contained in Article 1 Number 21 and 25 which reads: "Savings are deposits based on wadi'ah contracts or fund investments based on mudharabah contracts or other contracts that do not conflict with sharia principles. withdrawal can only be determined certain agreed upon, but can not be withdrawn by check, giro and or other similar tool with it ". "Financing is the provision of funds or claims equivalent to that in the form of: a. Profit sharing transactions in the form of Mudharabah and Musyarakah "(Indonesian Republic Law No. 21 of 2008).

Based on the above laws it can be presented that the transaction with the Mudharabah agreement has a legal basis in sharia banking products and can carry out business activities starting from the collection and / or distribution of financing funds. This fact can actually confirm that Mudharabah is part of the normative Islamic banking product and has a detailed order compared to regulations before 2008, either through the collection of funds relating to deposits in the form of deposits or temporary savings or the distribution of funds in the form of financing for the results.

In accordance with the explanation above, in the mudharabah agreement not only as a fund raiser but also as a contract that can distribute the profit-sharing financing funds, the mudharabah contract can be presented that the contract of cooperation for a business between the channeling of funds (Shahibul mal or Syariah Bank) as the provider of funds and the second party (Mudharib or Customer) as fund manager with an agreement to share the profits of the business in accordance with what has been agreed upon by both parties at the beginning of the agreement stated in the contract itself, while the loss will all be borne by the Islamic Bank if the error is caused by non-compliance intentionally and not negligence on the part of fund managers, and vice versa. Juridical consequences in the mudharabah agreement are referring to Sharia principles that are in accordance with Sharia banking laws sourced from the DSN-MUI Fatwa Agreement.

Based on the AAOIFI (Accounting and Auditing Organization of Islamic Financial Institutions) has provided standards for DPS, propositions and aspects related to regulations, reports and so on. According to the AAOIFI standards for the Sharia Supervisory Board should be independent and consist of scholars, jurists who are related to Islamic science and law. DPS can also consist of other experts in the field of Islamic financial institutions (economic, legal, accounting and other supporting fields) with scientific knowledge of Islamic laws relating to commercial transactions. DPS is mandated with the task of being able to direct, examine and supervise the activities of Islamic financial institutions to ensure that Islamic banking complies with sharia regulations and principles (Muhammad Ayub, 2009).

Related to DPS duties and responsibilities, as recorded in MUI Decree No. Kep-98 / MUI / 2001 concerning the composition of DPS-MUI is able to declassify as follows: First, to conduct periodic supervision on Islamic financial institutions under its supervision. Second, it is obliged to submit proposals for the development of sharia financial institution products that are monitored to the head of the institution concerned to DSN. Third, report the development of the products and operations of the Islamic financial institutions they supervise to the DSN at least 2 times in 1 fiscal year. Fourth, formulate problems that require mining that require discussion of DSN (Khaerul Umam, 2013).

The development of the Sharia financial industry, particularly in the banking sector in the State of Indonesia, which of course is in dire need of a governance system that guarantees the achievement of the established Sharia Financial Institution objectives. The governance system in Islamic financial institutions already has a very different approach to banking governance systems in general. This is due to the necessity for Islamic financial institutions to be able to ensure the implementation of sharia principles on all products issued by them, operational systems, practices and management in Islamic banking, so that they can become banks that comply with Islamic principles or Islamic law (Ali Rama, 2015).

In carrying out the contract that has been determined in Islamic banking, the Islamic banking must hold fast to the principles of Islamic banks that have been enforced by the National Sharia Council and Indonesian Ulama Council (DSNMUI) in order to remain in accordance with Islamic Sharia principles that prefer justice, Balance, Benefit and Universalism.

The principle that becomes the basis in Islamic banking is the principle of agreement agreed by both parties for financing, loan or deposit activities which at the beginning of the contract agreement that has been agreed based on Islamic law. In minimizing and avoiding irregularities and the possibility of non-compliance with sharia, DPS has a very important role and can help evaluate and detect all the implementation or implementation of sharia financial institutions against sharia principles. The existence of DPS is expected to be able to focus itself on the development and oversight of the Islamic financial institution industry on products and operational systems that are in accordance with Islamic principles or sharia principles.

DSN has the authority to give a reprimand to Islamic financial institutions that deviate from the established guidelines. This will be done if the National Sharia Board receives a report from the Sharia Supervisory Board that the Institute has deviated from the guidelines in accordance with Islamic law (Antonio, 2009). Therefore, in the Islamic banking industry, the services provided by Islamic banks to customers in general must comply with the principles of sharia which aim to gain benefits both materially and non-materially.

Application of the system in accordance with sharia principles, in its operation DPS supervises compliance with these principles and checks and makes recommendations for new products and contracts proposed by Islamic banking. Institutionally, the DPS has been able to play an optimal role for supervision of sharia compliance practices in sharia banking, thus each Sharia Bank management must be able to formalize the DPS role and involvement in ensuring risk management of non-compliance with sharia principles.

Therefore, Islamic banking must provide a space where there are staff of financial data services, financial reports, contracts, editors, contract processes implemented and so forth, so that the optimization of sharia principles runs optimally. The Mudharabah Principle is a part of sharia banking products that can be said to be unique, because in its implementation it has a philosophical difference between the conventional banking system and sharia banking which adheres to the principles of profit and loss based on the terms of the initial agreement. Financing based on mudharabah agreement is financing channeled by Sharia Bank To other parties (Rizal Yaya, 2009) with the aim of fulfilling all the interests of its customers who need capital or additional capital in running a productive business so can meet all of its economic needs (Mardani, 2015).

In the sacrificed implementation, the mudharabaah contract can be described based on the fatwa of the National Sharia Council and Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) Number 07 / DSN-MUI / IV / 2000 concerning Mudharabah Financing which can be a reference to Mudharabah financing. Mudharabah in its application in Islamic banking is usually applied in the form of financing and funding products (DSN-MUI No 07 / DSNMUI / IV / 2000). In the Easyarabah fund raising product can be applied with: First, term savings, namely savings that are special purpose such as, Haji savings, sacrifice savings and so on. Second, special deposits where funds are deposited by customers specifically for certain businesses such as mudharabah or ijarah only.

Whereas on the Mudharabah financing side, it can be applied with: First, Working capital financing, such as trade or service working capital. Second, Special Investment, which can be referred to as mudharabah muqayyadah where a special source of funds with a special distribution also with the conditions set by Shahibul mall (Muhammad Syafi'i Antonio, 2001). Based on the statement above, the researcher can interpret that in financing using the Mudharabah agreement, it is used for short-term cooperation only.

The argument of the statement is because if the investment is long-term, the capital or funds contained in the Islamic banking will settle and freeze up so it will take a long time to get the benefits expected by the Islamic banking. While other consequences are the Islamic banking will not be able to realize the system of revenue sharing to the depositors of funds (Muhammad, 2008).

V. Conclusion

The development of Indonesia's Islamic economic system resulted in the system in Islamic financial institutions requires compliance with Islamic principles or Islamic law. One institution that can guarantee to the system of adherence to Shariah compliance or Islamic law is maintained by DSN MUI, which provides the Shariah Compliance Supervisory Authority. Compliance is the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS). Implementation of the contractMudharabah in the Islamic banking system is a form of compliance banking to the principles of sharia that have been indicted by DPS MUI against Islamic banking. If violations in Islamic banking remain finalized it will damage the image and credibility of the

Islamic banking itself so that in the end it can reduce people's trust in Islamic banking which began to develop at this time.

References

- [1.] Ahmad Dahlan. (2012). *Bank Syariah Teori, praktik, kritik*. Yogyakarta: Teras.
- [2.] Antonio Syafi'i Muhammad. (2001). *Bank Syariah dari Teori ke Praktik*, Jakarta: Gema Insani.
- [3.] Ahmed, H. (2014). *Islamic and Shariah Compliance: A Produk Development Perspective*. *Journal Of Islamic Finance*.
- [4.] Arikunto, Suharsimi. (2000). *Manajemen Penelitian, cet Ke 5*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [5.] Ayub, Muhammad. (2009). *Understanding islamic Finance*, diterjemahkan oleh Aditya Wisnu, Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- [6.] Fatwa Dewan Syariah Nasional dan Majelis Ulama Indonesia Nomor 07 Tahun 2000 Tentang Pembiayaan Mudharabah (Qiradh).
- [7.] Firdaus Muhammad, Alshidiq Mukhtar, Hakim Azis Muhammad, Ghufron Sofiniyah. (2005). *Fatwa-fatwa Ekonomi Syariah Kontemporer*, Jakarta: Renaisan
- [8.] Hidayat Enang. (2016). *Transaksi Ekonomi Syari'ah*, Bandung: PT remaja Rosdakarya.
- [9.] Karim adiwarmam. (2006). *Bank Islam Analisis Fiqih dan Keuangan*, Jakarta: Radjagrafindo Persada.
- [10.] Khotibul Umam.(2015). *Perbankan Syariah (Dasar-dasar dan Dinamika Perkembangan di Indonesia)*, Jakarta: PT Rajagrafindo Persada.
- [11.] Luqman Nurhisam. (2016). *Kepatuhan Syariah (Syariah Compliance) dalam Industri Keuangan Syariah*. *Jurnal Hukum Islam Vol 23 No 1*, Universitas Islam Negeri Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta.
- [12.] Mardani. (2015). *Aspek lembaga Keuangan Syariah di Indonesia*. Jakarta: kencana.
- [13.] Muhammad. (2008). *Manajemen Pembiayaan Mudharabah di Perguruan Tinggi (strategi Memaksimalkan return dan Meminimalkan Risiko Pembiayaan di Bank Syariah Sebagai Akibat Masalah Agency)*, Jakarta: Rajawali Pres.
- [14.] Rama, Ali. (2015). *Analisis Siatem Tata Kelola Syariah Bagi Perbankan Syariah di Indonesi dan Malaysia*. *Jurnal Bimas Islam Vol 8 no. 1*, Dirjen Bimas, Jakarta.
- [15.] Sepky Mardian. (2015). *Tingkat kepatuhan Syariah di Lembaga Keuangan Syariah*. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Keuangan Islam Vol. 3 No 1 Syariah di Sekolah Tinggi Ekonomi Islam*.
- [16.] Syarif Hidayatullah. (2012). *Qawa'id Fiqiyyah dan Penerapannya dalam transaksi keuangan Syari'ah kontemporer*. Depok: Gramata Publishing.
- [17.] Umam Khotibul. (2011). *Legislasi Fiqih Ekonomi dan Penerapannya dalam Produk Perbankan Syariah di Indonesia*. Yogyakarta:BPFE.
- [18.] Umam Khaerul. (2013). *Manajemen Perbankan Syariah*, Bandung: Pustaka Setia.
- [19.] Undang-undang Republik Indonesia, Nomor 21 Tahun 2008 Tentang Perbankan Syariah.
- [20.] Wangsawidjaja. (2012). *Pembiayaan Bank Syari'ah*, Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- [21.] Yaya Rizal, Martawireja Erlangga Aji, Abdurahim Ahim. (2009). *Akuntansi Perbankan Syariah teori dan Praktik Kontemporer*, Jakarta; Salemba Empat.